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KAPMAGINAR

Paramata Bantogen was resting on Talatakan a Wato in the middle of the sea when all of a sudden, the Nori named Sampiri Kagadongan appeared flying near the Lakongan Malipantaw. Bantogen was amazed looking such pretty bird possibly owned by a beautiful royal princess. The prince asked about the bird's queen and region but the nori seemed silence and the question remained unanswered. The bird apologized for not answering directly so the nori asked the prince in return about his name, his king, region, and he has a sister. The prince answered politely thinking that the bird would reveal her secrets in return.

He introduced himself as Paramata Bantogen of Iliyan a Bembaran. Pasandalan a Morog is his king and Princess Lawanen as his sister. After hearing all the details, the nori answered in return stating that she came from Babalayan a Anonen where Bolentay a Maginar is her queen. The nori warned the prince from not crossing that place for anyone who dared to go lost their names and died.

The prince strongly decided to visit the place and so he asked the nori to describe the direction of the place. The nori explained that he has to pass a valley with its dangerous big river and crossing the plain with its deep stream. After moving forward, you will encounter an overgrown path of big tall palm trees. As you approach the place, beware for the flowers on top of the big rock spread a spell of rare perfume. At this point, the bird flapped her wings and made farewell to Bantogen.

Prince Bantogen dared to visit the place to look for the beautiful princess. He saw the valley with its rattling river. He crossed the deep stream and then there he saw the tall palm trees. He was trapped and could not escape until he asked help from the tonong named Inaikat a Lonsan. There appeared a strong wind, darkness, and rain to lash all the tall standing trees. Quickening his pace, he now reached the dreaded ring of fire with huge flame. He then took a huge flying leap jumping over the big monolith rock. He now soon arrived in front of the cogon grass, the place of perpetual daylight. Feeling trapped for five full days where no tree nor bush to cover him against the burning glare of sun rays, only his shield to cover his forehead. He now asked help from his own Pinatola i Kilid, a crocodile, to let some rain fall

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to refresh his suffering and requested Inodar a Magaog to bring him alongside the vast seashore. Now, there came a sudden change, a curtain of darkness hid the place. Not long after, a rain of hailstone befell the place. This time, he had arrived at the enchanted waters where the rocks were compared to human heads, the grave as human teeth, and the floating long seaweeds were really the hair of the dead. Trying to find a way out, he took a huge jump to the Lakongan Mariyammat then turning to the left, he once saw the huge palaw a Polo Manggar by a yellow sea with its green waters where witches loves to stay. Not long after, he now reached the igang tree with its giant roots where big crabs hid. He had now arrived at Talatalak a Wato, used as mortar to pond flowers by the women of Babalayan Anonen.

Prince Bantogen began to survey the place but he found no one, no painted torogan, only the ancient balete tree. As of this moment, he took a nap and suddenly dreamt of a beautiful princess addressing him to go at once for he shall be killed right there in Lakongan Mariyammat. In an instant, the prince awakened from his deep restful sleep. There appeared five huge crocodiles in front of him asking about his name, place, and his ruler. The prince told them the truth so they moved away, opening a path for the prince along the vast seashore. Along the way, he saw roof of houses but in closer look, these were not really houses but simply giant rocks, being fooled again by the tonongs. After some time had elapsed, a very old ugly woman appeared calling him sweetheart, offering him betelnut quid. The prince was truly angry and glared to the old ugly woman using his *kampilan i pagerag*. At last, darkness descended and the old ugly woman was nowhere to be seen. He once realized that he had again been fooled by the tonongs.

Suddenly, the *nori Sampiri Kagadongan* saw the prince and flew directly towards him, telling him that it is time to visit the spacious *lamin* of her queen, the *Walain a Maginar* of *Babalayan a Anonen*.

When the prince entered the palace, there a little girl greeted him, praising the prince for his bravery and persistence for anyone who dared to visit the palace lost his life. When the prince turned a good look to this little girl, he was no longer a little girl but a lovely princess. He suddenly became afraid and asked helped from the *Diwata I Ndawan* and *Diwata Makapanton* not to play jokes on him in this place. As soon as he had seen her, she just quickly disappeared. Before he began climbing the five steps, there appeared a princess offering him sliced of betelnut quid. The prince was so happy seeing the beautiful princess, ended up calling him dear brother telling him that she was his sister, and threatening him by placing a sharp knife pointing her towards her lovely head. After the acceptance of Bantogen, he now invited him to the upper part of the *lamin* where *Walain a Maginar* awaits. Her younger sister *Limbowan* asked her to offer betelnut quid to the prince but she refused for the prince caused her grief once.